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Investigation of Skylight Polarization Mode at Different Surface Albedo

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ABSTRACT

The sky polarization mode contains the location information for polarization navigation, which plays a vital role in realizing polarization navigation. It is formed by various internal and external factors such as atmospheric mode, gas molecules, aerosols, clouds, ground surface, time, and geographic location when sunlight passes through the atmosphere. It provides prominent information of directions, solar meridian, neutral points, and polarization azimuth, these are critical in navigation. Therefore, it is imperative to establish a theoretical model closer to the actual atmosphere for simulation analysis and conduct quantitative testing research on the sky polarization mode in the actual environment. Herein, the LibRadtran software is used to simulate and analyze the effect of different surface albedo at different surface types on the polarization degree and polarization azimuth. The actual tests are carried out on concrete, ocean, and asphalt surfaces. It is found that the surface albedo has a weakening effect on the polarization degree value on the same day and at the same time. In conclusion, the average reduction of the maximum polarization decreases with the increase of albedo size. Furthermore, the surface albedo has no evident effect on the polarization azimuth.

Keywords

Sky polarization mode, Surface albedo, Polarization degree, Polarization azimuth

Introduction

For skylight, polarization is a unique phenomenon that explains nature and shows the atmospheric turbidity, surface properties, and other reasons. Sun is the primary source of daylight. The sun's position primarily determines the skylight polarization pattern, based on Rayleigh scattering. The sunlight coming from the sun

is not polarized. Thus, When the sunlight collides with aerosol particles, polarization occurs, which is used in different daily applications such as navigation(1,2). Many biological species can detect their path when the sun is hidden and navigate back to their homes, such as honey bees and migratory animals(3–5). These animals use the skylight polarization as the source of directions(6).

The sky polarization mode in the actual environment is affected by the time information, geographic location, incident light wavelength, gas molecules concentration, aerosol size, cloud parameters, and surface albedo. The reflection from the ground will change the polarization characteristics of scattered light(7). It depends on the inherent properties of the reflective medium, the polarization state of the incident light, and the angle of incidence. Different surface types have different reflection characteristics and the reflection effect caused by different surface types can be represented by the surface albedo. The surface albedo refers to the ratio of the reflected flux of the incident light radiation on the surface to the radiant flux of the incident light, which determines the ability of the surface to absorb and reflect the light radiation. Due to the different geological and environmental characteristics, the surface changes significantly and the surface albedo varies greatly. Therefore, surface albedo is an important factor to study the sky polarization pattern under the actual atmosphere.

Over the years, many researchers have studied skylight polarization and extracted vital information. Previously, Vikings used a unique stone called sunstone for navigation when the clouds and foggy weather covered sunlight for direction(8). Moreover, skylight polarization patterns are investigated in various sky conditions using a point source polarimeter, where cloudy weather was found less evident than clear weather circumstances(9). Besides, a full-sky imaging polarimeter was used to study the polarization pattern of red, green, and blue light in overcast conditions and showed that the pattern is similar to clear skies(10). **Guan Le et al.** (11) measured the polarization pattern of skylights across the sea during day as well as night. The actual and theoretical results were compared using LibRadtran software.

Yi Liu et al. (12) used a polarization radiance distribution camera system to study the dependence of polarization and light intensity on wavelength, sun angle of zenith, and surface albedo. On another occasion, **A. Kreuter et al.** (13) investigated the influence of polarization degree and sky radiance at the wide range of surface albedo and aerosols. **Huijie et al** (14). used the liquid crystal variable retarders (LCVR) system. The setup was a complete imaging polarimeter, and the polarization patterns were studied in different cloud covers and aerosol optical thicknesses. A new solar meridian method was proposed while using the angle of polarization (AOP) map. In addition, **Wei Chen et al.** (15) studied the effect of aerosol optical depth and aerosol mode on sky polarization, which showed that the polarization pattern of the sky is different in scattering and absorbing aerosol mode.

The current studies on sky polarization mode mainly focus on the theoretical level of simulation research. Herein, the MYSTIC algorithm of the Monte Carlo method is used to solve the vector radiative transfer

equation. The sky polarization model close to the actual atmosphere was employed successfully. The LibRadtran software is used to simulate and analyze the influence of surface albedo and the relationship between surface albedo and maximum polarization degree. Furthermore, the image-based sky polarization test system is used to carry out the actual test under different surfaces. The simulation and experimental evolution of sky polarization mode are taken for the application of polarization navigation.

Materials and methods

Radiative Transfer Monte Carlo method (MYSTIC):

Polarized light in the sky is altered during the transmission process through the absorption, scattering, and reflection of air contaminants, aerosol atoms, clouds, plus the ground surface.

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of skylight polarization mode

A general process is shown in Fig. 1. The clouds and aerosol particles collide by sunlight exposure in the atmosphere. Some of the photons are absorbed in aerosol particles, some of them reflect, and the rest reach the ground after several collisions(11). The MYSTIC algorithm of the Monte Carlo method in LibRadtran software is used to resolve the radiative transfer equation. The MYSTIC algorithm of the Monte Carlo method effectively solves the complicated radiative transfer equation for complex weather and establishes the sky polarization mode close to the actual atmosphere(16).

The radiative transfer equation is solved using eq. (1). In eq. (1), I is the atmospheric radiation Intensity, τ is the optical thickness, φ is the azimuth angle corresponding to the sunlight, ω is the single scattering albedo, F_0 is the incident radiant flux density of sunlight at the top of the atmosphere. μ_0 and φ_0 are depicting solar zenith angle and solar azimuth angle of cosine, correspondingly, M is Mueller matrix and B is Planck function of temperature(17). By adjusting parameters in LibRadtran software, such as the solar location, aerosol sorts, the water cloud's optical properties, and the photon quantity, the photons approach the earth. As a result, the

Rayleigh scattering model close to the realistic skylight polarization model at different surface types is displayed(18).

$$\mu \frac{dI(\tau, \mu, \varphi)}{d\tau} = -I(\tau, \mu, \varphi) + \frac{\omega}{4\pi} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-1}^1 M(\tau, \mu, \varphi, \mu', \varphi') I(\tau, \mu', \varphi') d\mu d\varphi + \frac{\omega}{4\pi} F_0 \exp\left(\frac{-\tau}{\mu_0}\right) M(\tau, \mu, \varphi, -\mu_0, \varphi_0)[1,0,0,0] + (1 - \omega)B(T)[1,0,0,0]^T \tag{1}$$

Experimental Setup

The MATLAB software is used to solve the Stokes Vector S. The AOP and DOP in skylight polarization patterns are calculated using the Stokes vector. The Stokes vector is $S = [I Q U V]^T$, where I denotes total light intensity, Q and U are linearly polarized in two orthogonal directions, and V is circular polarization which is taken as zero(19). The Stokes Vector S is simplified with the Mueller matrix represented by M. The relationship between Stokes Vector S and Mueller matrix M using the linear transformation process is $S = MS$ (20). The actual polarization method is expressed using Mueller matrix M as:

$$M = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \cos 2\varphi & \sin 2\varphi & 0 \\ \cos 2\varphi & \cos^2 2\varphi & \cos 2\varphi \sin 2\varphi & 0 \\ \sin 2\varphi & \cos 2\varphi \sin 2\varphi & \sin^2 2\varphi & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

Conversely, φ denotes the angle formed by the transmission and the reference planes, the renowned intensity of light Stokes vector equation is described as:

$$I'(\varphi) = \frac{1}{2}(I + Q \cos 2\varphi + U \sin 2\varphi) \tag{3}$$

In this experimental setup, the polarizer is rotated at an angle of 0° , $\frac{\pi}{4}$, and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ respectively. By using equation (3);

$$\begin{cases} I' (0^\circ) = \frac{1}{2}(I + Q) \\ I' \left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) = \frac{1}{2}(I + U) \\ I' \left(\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \frac{1}{2}(I - Q) \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

When these parameters of the Stokes vector in equation 4 are calculated, then the polarization degree (P) and polarization azimuth (X) are calculated as:

$$\text{Polarization Degree} = P = \frac{\sqrt{Q^2 + U^2}}{I} \tag{5}$$

$$\text{Polarization Azimuth} = X = \frac{1}{2} \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{U}{Q}\right) \tag{6}$$

The experimental setup includes a DSLR camera, fisheye lens, a linear polarizer, and a tripod. The details of the experimental parts are represented in Table 1. It can measure the 180-degree field of view. A rotatable

linear polarizer is placed on the lens of the camera. The camera is fixed on a tripod to shoot pictures at different elevation angles and azimuth angles, as presented in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. The full-sky imaging system

Table 1. The full-sky imaging system

Part	Labels	Features
Camera	D750	Model
	3008x4512	Dimensions
Polarizer	400-700 nm	Wavelength range
	98±2	Polarizer efficiency
	77 mm	Thickness
Fisheye lens	F3.5-F22	Aperture
	180°	Field of view
	8 mm	Focal length
	1/4000	Exposure time

Before the test, a wide field of view is selected to ensure no shelter in front of the lens. The test system is assembled, and the main optical axis of the fisheye lens is fixed perpendicular to the ground. Finally, it is corrected with the digital leveler. The north directions can be located by compass for the zero reading. After the adjustments, the test is carried out according to Beijing time (GMT+8). The linear polarizer is rotated at angles 0°, 45°, and 90°, respectively. The real-time data of each angle is collected and arranged. The polarization data is processed according to the test principle, and three images are processed for a specific

time by MATLAB after the test. Initially, the program reads the light intensity information of each pixel in the image through RGB mode to obtain the light intensity values at each test time. Afterward, the program successively substitutes the value into the formulas to obtain the polarization degree and polarization azimuth. Three pictures at different angles display the sky polarization mode of each test time.

Experiment and Results

Reflections from the ground change the polarization properties of scattering light. Different surface types have been chosen for the simulation in the LibRadtran software to observe the influence of surface albedo on sky polarization mode. Figure 3 demonstrates the simulation results of the different surface types on the maximum polarization degree and polarization azimuth. At 11:00 a.m. on October 12, 2021, the sky polarization pattern is taken in the Dalian area (38.8 N, 121.6 E). The Ozone concentration is taken at 300DU and the wavelength is 480nm. The aerosol surface types are selected as Oat field, lawn, loam, wetland, dry land, sand, and snow. The black line in Fig. 3(a) and 3(b) is representing the solar meridian and the polarization degree values are 0.7818, 0.7517, 0.711, 0.6674, 0.6345, 5809, 0.4019, respectively. The maximum polarization degree is the smallest on the snow surface because of the large surface albedo. It can be seen in Fig. 3 that different surface types have different properties, and the influence on the polarization azimuth is negligible in theoretical conditions. The polarization azimuth is always stable in every case, and it's along ± 90 .

Fig. 3. Simulation result of skylight polarization of different surface types (a) Simulation result of polarization degree (b) Simulation result of polarization azimuth.

The experiments are done in two different groups of surface albedo to compare the theoretical and actual environmental results. The first group is concrete and asphalt surfaces, and the surface albedo is 0.25-0.7 and 0.05-0.2, respectively. The second group consists of ocean and asphalt surfaces, and the surface albedo is 0.1-0.2 and 0.05-0.2, respectively. The albedo values of common surface types are shown in Table 2 (21,22).

Table 2. Different surface albedo sizes

Surface type	Asphalt	Concrete	Grass	Oceans	Ice	Trees	Fresh Snow
Albedo	0.05-0.2	0.25-0.7	0.25-0.3	0.1-0.2	0.3-0.5	0.15-0.18	0.81-0.88

Two locations, the concrete surface (38.6 N, 121.30 E) and the asphalt surface (38.64 N, 121.26 E), are selected respectively for the sky polarization mode test. The test locations are in Ganjingzi District, Dalian city, Liaoning province, China. The test date is October 12, 2021. The weather is clear, and the test time is 9:00-16:00. The test results are shown in Fig.4, where the black line represents the solar meridian. Figure 4 (a) and 4(c) are the polarization degree charts. The polarization degree value is high at the beginning and then decreases along the solar meridian direction. The maximum polarization degree value is different at each test time. In Fig. 4 (a) and 4(c), at (9:00-11:00) the polarization degree value is high. It reaches the lowest value at 11:00-13:00 when the sun altitude is high. The polarization degree value follows the Raleigh scattering theory and it is zero at the neutral point at the sun position. Positive values are frequently produced by primary scattering of air particles, whereas negative values are produced by varied time scattering. The zero-point polarization arises in the sky when positive and negative values collide. These are the points of zero polarization or neutral points(23). Figure 4 (b) and (d) are the polarization azimuth test charts. The polarization azimuth distribution is always stable and is distributed along the solar meridian at $\pm 90^\circ$. Due to the difference in albedo between concrete and asphalt surfaces, the maximum polarization degree value at the same time is different.

Fig. 4. Testing polarization mode of asphalt and concrete surface (a) Polarization degree of asphalt surface (b) Polarization azimuth of asphalt surface (c) Polarization degree of concrete surface (d) Polarization azimuth of concrete surface

The maximum polarization degree value of the concrete and asphalt surfaces is shown in Fig. 5. The maximum polarization value of the concrete surface under each test time is smaller than that of the asphalt surface, indicating the same day and the same time in Fig. 5. The larger the surface albedo, the smaller the maximum polarization degree. It can be seen from the data calculation in Fig. 5 that the average maximum polarization degree value of the concrete surface is less than the asphalt surface.

Fig. 5. Maximum polarization degree values of asphalt and concrete surface at different times

The test locations are in Shahekou District, Dalian city, Liaoning province, China. It is located on the Yellow Sea. The ocean surface (38.52 N, 121.35 E) and the asphalt surface (38.58 N, 121.30 E) are selected for the sky polarization mode test. The test date is December 28, 2021, the weather is sunny and the test time is 9:00-16:00. The results are shown in Fig. 6 (a), (b), (c), and (d), respectively, where the black line is the solar meridian. Figure 6 (a) and (c) represent the polarization degree test charts. The polarization degree is similar to theoretical studies of Rayleigh scattering. The polarization degree value is zero at the neutral point, increasing and decreasing along the solar meridian direction. In Fig. 6(a) and 6(c), at (9:00-11:00) at the beginning the polarization degree value is high. The polarization degree value reaches the lowest value at 11:00-13:00 when the sun altitude is high. Different albedos have different effects at the same time in experiments, and the polarization degree value is different. Figure 6(b) and (d) represent the solar meridian's polarization azimuth at ± 90 . The pattern is always stable, and according to Rayleigh scattering theory as the day conditions were similar to the ideal condition. Ocean and asphalt surfaces have different albedos where the maximum polarization degree value depends on albedo size.

Fig. 6. Testing polarization mode of asphalt and ocean surface (a) Polarization degree of asphalt surface (b) Polarization azimuth of asphalt surface (c) Polarization degree of ocean surface (d) Polarization azimuth of ocean surface

The maximum polarization degree value of ocean and asphalt surfaces is shown in Fig. 7. The maximum polarization degree value of the ocean surface at each time in Fig. 7 is lower than that of the asphalt surface, indicating the same time. The average polarization degree value of the ocean surface is less than the asphalt surface. Figure 5 and Figure 7 reveal that albedo size has more effect on the maximum polarization degree value with an increase in albedo size. The double aperture effect is more visible in the morning and about sunset when the sun is at its nadir. The polarization degree is the lowest in the sun direction of the incident, indicating the atmospheric neutral point. The polarization degree rises from the center to the surrounding. In contrast, the polarization degree achieves a maximum value and begins to drop perpendicular to the sun's incident direction. Due to the presence of the sun and anti-sun neutral points called Babinet and Arago Points. A double aperture effect appears when these two points interact.

Fig. 7. Maximum polarization degree values of asphalt and ocean surface at different times

Conclusion

This paper covers the investigation mechanism of sky polarization mode and its key influencing factors using the theory of atmospheric radiative transfer model. To solve the vector radiative transfer equation, the Monte Carlo method is used. The MSTIC algorithm of the vector radiative transfer model is applied to solve the atmospheric radiative transfer equation, and the sky polarization model is established close to the actual environment. The LibRadtran software is employed to simulate and analyze the influence of different surface albedo on the maximum polarization degree.

The Stokes vector technique of sky polarization mode and its test concept was used to construct an image-based sky polarization mode test system. The actual environment tests are taken at different surface types to check the maximum polarization degree value and polarization azimuth influence. It is found that different surface albedo has a different effect on polarization mode on the same day and same time. The maximum polarization degree has more noticeable effects than the polarization azimuth. There is no obvious effect found on the polarization azimuth as the surface albedo size changed but the polarization degree value decreased with the increase in albedo size.

Also, the double aperture effect is seen when the solar altitude angle is low. While only one convergence point is noted in the daytime. Navigation information from the polarization pattern leads to accurate directions of places.

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